

A Synthesis of ($\pm$) Cryptone

R. C. Banerjee

An unambiguous synthesis of ($\pm$) cryptone and ($\pm$) cryptol is reported*.

Cryptone, a monoterpenoid compound of natural origin¹ was first identified as 4-isopropylcyclohex-2-en-1-one (I) by Wallach². Later, it was synthesised by a number of workers³ from *p*-isopropylanisole by application of the Birch reduction using either sodium-ethanol-liquid ammonia⁴ or lithium-ethanol-liquid ammonia⁵. The hydrolysis of the resultant 2,5-dihydro-4-isopropylanisole, however, always led to a mixture of ($\pm$) cryptone (I) and its $\beta\gamma$ -isomer (II) (cf. Birch⁶), the latter occurring to the extent of about 40%. In course of our investigation of certain cyclic β -diketones^{7,8}, we found that an unambiguous synthesis of ($\pm$) cryptone could be achieved from 4-isopropyl-1,3-dione (III) as follows.

The diketone (III) was prepared according to the method of Bardhan *et al.*⁹ and also more conveniently by an alternative route from ethyl α -isopropylacetoacetate by successive cyanoethylation¹⁰, hydrolysis, esterification, and the Claisen condensation of the resultant ethyl 5-oxo-4-isopropylhexanoate (IV). The diketone (III) was converted into 1-isobutyloxy-4-isopropylcyclohex-1-en-3-one in good yield; the latter was reduced

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1. Berry *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1448; Cahn *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1931, 1366; Wienhaus and Striegler, Schimmel's Report, 1937, p. 91.
2. Wallach, *Ber. Chem. Ges.*, 1905, 343, 30.
3. Bhati, *Curr. Sci.*, 1952, 21, 314; Talukdar and Mukherjee, *Science & Culture*, 1952, 18, 150; Rao and Dev, *this Journal*, 1950, 33, 539.
4. Birch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 430.
5. Wilds and Nelson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5360.
6. Birch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 593.
7. Bardhan and Banerjee, *ibid.*, 1956, 1806.
8. Banerjee, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, 21B, 285.
9. Bardhan *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 3195.
10. Misra and Shukla, *this Journal*, 1952, 29, 456.

with lithium aluminium hydride and then acidified to afford the unsaturated ketone (I), b.p. 704-105°/17 mm; n_D^{25} , 1.4790; d_4^{25} 0.9311; $[R_L]_D$ 42.07; λ_{max}^{EtOH} 227 and 313 m μ (log ϵ , 4.06 and 1.67 respectively), identical with (±) cryptone¹¹ in all respects. The dinitrophenylhydrazones, m.p. 136°, and semicarbazone, m.p. 196-96.5°, agree well with those reported in the literature³. (±) Cryptone thus obtained was further reduced to *trans*-(±) cryptol¹² (V) by lithium aluminium hydride, the latter being characterised through the formation of 3,5-dinitrobenzoate, m.p. 108°.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 5-Oxo-4-isopropylhexanoate (IV).—Ethyl α -isopropyl- α -(2-cyanoethyl)-acetate (28 g.), glacial acetic acid (40 ml), and HCl (conc., 160 ml) were refluxed on a sand bath for 10 hrs. After removal of the acetic acid in the water pump, the residue was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution dried (Na₂SO₄), solvent evaporated, and then distilled. *5-Oxo-4-isopropylhexanoic acid* was obtained as a colorless oil (14.8 g.), b.p. 147-49°/5mm, and esterified by boiling with 3% ethanolic hydrogen chloride. The *ethyl ester* (IV) had b.p. 98-100°/5 mm. (Found: C, 65.8; H, 9.9. C₁₁H₂₀O₃ requires C, 66.0; H, 10.0%).

4-Isopropyl-1,3-dione (III).—(a). The preceding ester (21.5 g.) was heated with an ethanolic solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (2.5 g.) and anhydrous ethanol (80 ml) for 20 hours. Most of the ethanol was removed in the water pump, the residue cooled, diluted with water, and any neutral matter removed by extraction with ether. The aqueous alkaline solution was carefully acidified and the diketone (III) separated as an oil (16 g.) which solidified on scratching. It crystallised from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 106-107° (Bardhan *et al.*⁹ report m.p. 106-107°).

(b). The yield of the diketone in the above reaction was much improved by the use of sodium hydride in place of sodium ethoxide. A mixture of ethyl 5-oxo-4-isopropylhexanoate (IV) (25.6 g.), sodium hydride (6.8 g.), dry benzene (120 ml), and one drop of ethanol was heated under reflux in an atmosphere of nitrogen with stirring for 2 hours. The solution was cooled, decomposed with ice-water, and the aqueous layer separated. Acidification of the alkaline solution afforded diketone (III) (22 g.) as a solid, m.p. 106°.

1-Isobutyloxy-cyclohex-1-en-3-one.—A mixture of the above diketone (13 g.), isobutanol (15 ml), dry benzene (60 ml), and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (0.5 g.) was refluxed for 14 hours using a Dean and Stark water separator, when almost the theoretical amount of water was set free. The solution was cooled and poured into an ice-cold saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate. The benzene layer was separated, washed with 2% NaOH solution, then with water, dried (MgSO₄), and the solvent evaporated. The residue was distilled to a colorless liquid (13.2 g.), b.p. 139-41°/10 mm. (Found: C, 74.1; H, 10.4. C₁₀H₁₆O requires C, 74.3; H, 10.5%).

(±) *Cryptone* (I).—A solution of the foregoing ketone (13.2g.) in dry ether (25 ml) was slowly added to a stirred slurry of LiAlH₄ (2 g.) in ether (70 ml) and the whole refluxed gently for 1hr. It was cooled and decomposed cautiously with 15% aqueous sulphuric

11. Cooke and Macbeth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1411.

12. *Ibid.*, 1939, 1531.

acid. The ethereal layer was separated, washed with water, dried (K_2CO_3), and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The residual ketonic material was distilled to furnish a colorless oil (7.8 g.), b. p. $104-106^\circ/17$ mm. (Found: C, 78.1; H, 9.9. Calc. for $C_9H_{14}O$: C, 78.2; H, 10.1%). The liquid had a characteristic smell and the following physical properties: n_D^{25} , 1.4790; D_4^{25} 0.9311; $[R_L]_D$ 42.07 (calc. 41.10); λ_{max}^{EtOH} 227 and 313 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.06 and 1.67 respectively). Cooke and Macbeth¹¹ report λ_{max} 226.3 and 314 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.1 and 1.56 respectively). The semicarbazone formed readily from ethanol in white needles, m.p. $196-96.5^\circ$. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 8.7. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{17}ON_3$: C, 61.5; H, 8.7%). The dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethanol in deep orange-red plates, m.p. $136-36.5^\circ$; λ_{max}^{EtOH} 375 μ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.42). (Found: C, 56.4; H, 5.6. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{18}O_4N_4$: C, 56.6; H, 5.6%).

($\pm$) *Cryptol*.—($\pm$) Cryptone (10 g.) was reduced by $LiAlH_4$ (1.5 g.) in ethereal solution (50 ml) and the product worked up in the usual way. On distillation, it afforded an oil (9.2 g.), b. p. $95-100^\circ/10$ mm. (Found: C, 76.0; H, 11.5. Calc. for $C_9H_{16}O$: C, 77.1; H, 11.4%). It afforded a 3,5-dinitrobenzoate which crystallised from ethanol in light yellow plates, m.p. 108° . (Found: C, 57.3; H, 5.3. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{18}O_6N_2$: C, 57.5; H, 5.4%).

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA 9.

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